

INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHER WHEN WORKING WITH DISABLED CHILDREN WHO ARE HOME-SCHOOLED

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Abstract. *Education involves mandatory comprehensive assistance to children with disabilities who do not have the opportunity to attend an educational organization. Special learning conditions are created for such children (for example, home-based learning) so that students have equal opportunities to master the educational program, taking into account their special educational needs. At the same time, children studying at home are full participants in the educational process.*

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Modern education involves mandatory comprehensive assistance to children with disabilities who do not have the opportunity to attend an educational organization. Special learning conditions are created for such children (for example, home-based learning) so that students have equal opportunities to master the educational program, taking into account their special educational needs. At the same time, children studying at home are full participants in the educational process. In order to create an inclusive classroom where all students are respected, it is important to use language that prioritizes the student over his or her disability. Disability labels can be stigmatizing and perpetuate false stereotypes where students who are disabled are not as capable as their peers. In general, it is appropriate to reference the disability only when it is pertinent to the situation. For instance, it is better to say “The student, who has a disability” rather than “The disabled student” because it places the importance on the student, rather than on the fact that the student has a disability. Disabilities can be temporary (such as a broken arm), relapsing and remitting, or long-term. Types of disabilities may include:

Hearing loss

Low vision or blindness

Learning disabilities, such as Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, dyslexia, or dyscalculia

Mobility disabilities

Chronic health disorders, such as epilepsy, Crohn’s disease, arthritis, cancer, diabetes, migraine headaches, or multiple sclerosis

Psychological or psychiatric disabilities, such as mood, anxiety and depressive disorders, or Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)

Asperger’s disorder and other Autism spectrum disorders

Traumatic Brain Injury

Students may have disabilities that are more or less apparent. For instance, you may not know that a student has epilepsy or a chronic pain disorder unless she chooses to disclose or an incident arises. These “hidden” disorders can be hard for students to disclose because many people

assume, they are healthy because “they look fine.” In some cases, the student may make a seemingly strange request or action that is disability-related. For example, if you ask the students to rearrange the desks, a student may not help because he has a torn ligament or a relapsing and remitting condition like Multiple Sclerosis. Or, a student may ask to record lectures because she has dyslexia and it takes longer to transcribe the lectures.

I would like to share my work experience with students studying under an individual educational program (disabled children, with musculoskeletal disorders) who, for health reasons, cannot attend classes with other children and are home-schooled.

Learning a foreign language is very important for such children, as they understand that for health reasons they will most likely carry out their future professional activities from home. Therefore, the motivational focus on learning a foreign language is quite high. They associate their future life with programming or translation activities, since both can be done remotely.

The project activity has proven itself well. My children really like this form of work, as it involves independent research of something new. Here are a few projects that home-based students have completed:

- "My best friend is a translator" (it's no secret that when preparing homework, students often resort to the help of online translators to find out the meaning of a word or expression. But are all online translators the same? This question was studied and presented by the 8th grade student Polina D.)

- "Internet Security" (often, when you visit a site, it gives out some content for download. Moreover, all information is in English, and those who do not know a foreign language can download a malicious program or virus to their computer. Here are some commands: "install - install", "download - download", "press - click", "delete - delete", <attach - attach>, knowledge of the translation of which will help to avoid unwanted downloading of programs. This work was carried out by a student of the 9th grade Timur K.).

Gaming activity is also an important innovative element of the educational process in a foreign language lesson. In order to motivate the child to learn English, so that the student's interest is not lost during the lesson, since the student works one-on-one with the teacher for all 40 minutes, a change of activity is very important. And the game helps a lot in this.

The choice of the game is limited by the fact that one (student) or two (teacher and student) people can participate in it.

Since games are different (phonetic, grammatical, lexical, role-playing, spelling, etc.), I will give an example of some of them.

When working with children with disabilities, the leading role in my lessons is played by role-playing games that can be adjusted to absolutely any educational situation: in a store, in a cinema, on the street, in a cafe, etc. Children willingly try on the role of a buyer, director, sports coach, movie star, actively use the studied vocabulary and grammatical constructions are used. Such complex exercises aimed at the formation of lexical and grammatical skills, listening skills, speaking skills, are easily performed by children in a playful way.

Making a crossword puzzle. It would seem that there is nothing new to come up with here? But, oddly enough, in modern English textbooks, this type of work with vocabulary is practically absent. When the topic is completed completely, as a reinforcement, the children make up a crossword puzzle. At the same time, you need to independently come up with definitions of words in English (when the children were in grades 4, 5, instead of definitions, they drew objects on the

topic of "Clothes", "Food", "Furniture"). This type of exercise develops lexical and grammatical skills.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the main part of the educational process is occupied by the practice of the English language. And since children with disabilities are active computer users, communicate with friends on social networks, learn about the world around them through the world Wide Web, this language orientation is dictated by modern practical necessity.

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